

Insight Digital Lending pathways
in Italy, Poland and Spain

(i)SDL Insight

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Final report

The authors of this report are:

Deborah De Angelis, Laura Sinigaglia, Silvana Mangiaracina, Stefania Marzocchi, Ginevra Peruginelli, Silvia Giannini and Debora Mazza, for the graphic design.

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The publication is issued as part of the Knowledge Rights 21 project, funded by Arcadia, a family charitable foundation, through the Knowledge Rights 21 (KR21) programme managed by IFLA, in partnership with LIBER and SPARC Europe.

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Abstract

The *(i)SDL Insight - Digital Lending pathways in Italy, Poland and Spain* project, supported by Knowledge Rights 21 and coordinated by Deborah De Angelis, the Italian coordinator of KR21, aims to analyse digital lending (eLending), with a particular focus on (independent) Secure Digital Lending (iSDL) in libraries across three European Union countries: Poland, Spain, and Italy. Through the dissemination of a survey, the project examines the factors and barriers that affect the implementation of (i)SDL, as well as the current state of practice, including digital lending models, types of materials lent, user demand, and future outlook, serving as a starting point for developing strategies to overcome these challenges.

Participating in the project are:

- the [DDA Law Firm](#), project coordinator;
- [CLAKP](#) - Copyright Law and Access to Knowledge Policies Group, a multi-stakeholder initiative coordinated by the Institute of Legal Informatics and Judicial Systems (IGSG) of the National Research Council (CNR) and of the “*Dario Nobili*” Library of the CNR Research Area, the Library and Scientific Documentation Center of the CNR Research Area in Pisa, and the DDA Law Firm (Italy);
- [Centrum Cyfrowe](#) (Poland);
- [Fesabid](#) (Spain).

The present final report is a summary of the results derived from three national reports:

- **Italy:** ([DDA Law Firm](#), [CLAKP](#) - Copyright Law and Access to Knowledge Policies Group of the IGSG - Institute of Legal Informatics and Judicial Systems/CNR - National Research Council, the “*Dario Nobili*” Library of the CNR, the Library and Scientific Documentation Center of the CNR Research Area in Pisa for Italy)¹;
- **Spain:** ([Fesabid](#))², and
- **Poland** ([Centrum Cyfrowe](#))³.

Executive Summary

The comparative survey conducted across libraries in Italy, Spain, and Poland reveals a shared aspiration to implement (independent) Secure Digital Lending (i)SDL services, but significant systemic barriers continue to hinder progress.

¹ Available here: <https://zenodo.org/records/15800408>

² Available here: <https://zenodo.org/records/15801240>

³ Available here: <https://zenodo.org/records/15804604>

Across all contexts, the main barriers identified are legal uncertainty, technological limitations, inadequate funding, and insufficient human resource capacity. Many respondents perceive the legal framework as ambiguous or unknown, creating institutional hesitation and a lack of confidence in offering (i)SDL services. From a technological perspective, most libraries lack essential digitisation equipment, DRM systems, and archiving solutions, alongside staff trained to manage these processes effectively.

Despite these challenges, there is a strong desire for progress. Libraries emphasise, above all, the **need to improve the legal framework** by establishing clear guidelines and legislative support that would enable them to implement (i)SDL services securely and lawfully. This fundamental step is accompanied by calls for **dedicated funding schemes** to overcome financial constraints and support infrastructure development. Respondents also stress the importance of **investing in capacity-building programmes** to equip staff with the necessary legal and technical expertise, as well as **developing collaborative infrastructures** that allow institutions to share technological resources, reduce individual burdens, and build collective capacity. Progress in these areas may well be connected. Notably, clear legal authorisation for (i)SDL has the potential to provide the certainty required to justify investment and resource allocation.

Overall, while adoption of (i)SDL remains limited today, libraries recognise its potential to support digital transformation, enhance user access (particularly for remote, rural, or disadvantaged communities), and preserve cultural resources for future generations. However, without legal clarity, structural investments, and coordinated policy commitment at both national and international levels, the opportunity to fully embrace digital lending and fulfil the library's evolving mission in the digital age will remain unrealised. As such, legal reform indeed.

Improving the legal framework, and ensuring the relevant funding, skills, and infrastructure is essential for libraries to realise the full potential of Secure Digital Lending in Europe.

I. The Context

Through the dissemination of a survey, the project aims to gather information from libraries in Italy, Poland and Spain concerning (independent) Secure Digital Lending (iSDL) — e-lending based on paper books digitised and lent by libraries, using technological protection measures to prevent non-legitimate uses (for instance, measures to limit the lending time, to prevent downloading, etc., often called DRM - Digital Rights Management Systems).

(i)SDL is the digital counterpart to traditional lending of physical books. A digitally secure environment allows libraries to lend out digitised works from their print collection under the same conditions as traditional lending (one copy, one user, for a limited time). In this way, libraries can fulfil their fundamental purpose of providing access to culture and knowledge by utilising existing technological possibilities and enabling, among other things, users to

remotely access content that would otherwise be accessible only in person.

In this context, the Judgment of the Court of Justice of the European Union of 10 November 2016 on e-lending by libraries in the EU⁴ is relevant, in that it provides a basis for (independent) Secure Digital Lending [(i)SDL]. The Court ruled⁵ that digital lending can fall under the public lending exception in EU law, provided it follows a "one copy, one user" model, aligning with Directive 2006/115/EC⁶. According to the decision, for e-lending to be lawful, libraries must hold a legitimate digital copy. The Court did not address whether libraries can digitise their books under EU exceptions, though the Advocate General supported this possibility. Nonetheless, a lack of effort to reform national laws to provide clarity around this point, as well as the reluctance of some publishers has hindered widespread adoption of e-lending across the EU⁷.

The concept and features of (i)SDL have been further elaborated in the report *eBooks and Secure Digital Lending in European Libraries*, published by Knowledge Rights 21⁸. According to this report, e-lending within the (i)SDL framework is characterised by several key features. First, loans must be carried out by clearly defined institutions, such as libraries, that are open to the public and do not derive any direct or indirect economic or commercial advantage from lending activities. Second, the lending itself involves a digital copy of a book, and this is provided under the "one copy, one user" principle, ensuring that each digital loan mirrors the limitations of physical lending.

Moreover, the lending process can take place in two different ways: a mimetic approach, where users are able to download an electronic copy, or a quasi-mimetic approach, where users access the work through streaming. Importantly, lending is always for a limited period, after which the user can no longer access the e-book. Another critical feature is that libraries must hold a digital copy from a lawful source, although they are permitted to digitise a legally acquired print copy for this purpose. Under this model, e-lending also generates a right to remuneration (known as Public Lending Right, PLR) in accordance with the EU Rental and Lending Directive⁹. Finally, the model ensures that no data, including the personal data of library users, is transferred to publishers or third parties, protecting user privacy and institutional independence.

⁴The Judgement C-174/15 (Vereniging Openbare Bibliotheken-VOB case) is available here: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex:62015CJ0174>

⁵The possibility of digitising paper books is based on the interpretation provided by CJEU TU Darmstadt ruling (Technische Universität Darmstadt v Eugen Ulmer KG. Case C117/13).

⁶The Directive 2006/115/EC is available here: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2006/115/oj/eng>

⁷Gliściński, Konrad, Towards e-Lending by Libraries. Judgment of the Court of Justice of the European Union of 10 November 2016, C-174/15 (December 16, 2024). Available at <https://ssrn.com/abstract=5063346>;

<https://ruj.uj.edu.pl/server/api/core/bitstreams/7d14abee-35c6-4dcf-86e0-902cc02a6da4/content>

⁸ Available at <https://www.knowledgerights21.org/reports/ebook-sdl-report/>

⁹ Directive 2006/115/EC of the European Parliament and of the Council of 12 December 2006 on rental right and lending right and on certain rights related to copyright in the field of intellectual property, <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/eli/dir/2006/115/oj/eng>

(i)SDL is designed to balance the rights of authors and publishers with the fundamental public mission of libraries. By creating a secure, legal, and technologically robust environment for digital lending, (i)SDL has the potential to transform library services and ensure that they remain inclusive and relevant.

As a step on from the published report, this analysis takes the next step of investigating current practices and perspectives around (i)SDL in Italy, Poland and Spain both to assess whether libraries, are currently able to provide the services for which they are intended and to reconstruct the current (i)SDL landscape - shedding light on existing practices, legal and technical challenges, and the level of user demand.

II. The Survey

The survey aims to investigate (i)SDL in Italy, Poland, and Spain from the perspective of libraries, identifying legal, technological, and infrastructure barriers, the risk of opposition, and the associated human resources and financial burdens. The survey aims to gather initial information on the topic, laying the groundwork for future initiatives by helping to understand critical questions around the implementation of implementing (i)SDL. Through this, the ambition is to outline a course of action to enable libraries to disseminate culture and knowledge in the digital environment.

The survey was structured to take into account several essential elements for an optimal response outcome. It was also designed to be easy to understand and navigate to encourage participation - a vital step given the very specific subject matter.

The survey was divided into eight sections: I. Library profile, II. Digital lending, III. Legal barriers, IV. Technological and infrastructure barriers, V. Risk of opposition, VI. Human resources, VII. Financial barriers, VIII. Others. In addition, some free-text comments were given following several questions.

The questionnaire was administered anonymously, and the information needed to identify the type of library for which the respondent was responding, as well as the role covered by the respondent, was requested.

The Italian partners of the project drafted the survey questions. These were [DDA Law Firm](#), [CLAKP](#) (Copyright Law and Access to Knowledge Policies Group), conceived and developed by the IGSG (Institute of Legal Informatics and Judicial Systems)/CNR (National Research Council). A draft was then shared with the foreign partners: [Centrum Cyfrowe](#) for Poland, and [Fesabid](#) for Spain. They provided interesting suggestions and valuable comments to define the final draft, which was further revised by Stephen Wyber of Knowledge Rights 21 and then translated into Italian, Polish and Spanish.

Each country sent the invitation email through its designated channels on February 5, 2025,

and the questionnaire remained available until March 3, 2025.

In **Italy**, the most authoritative directory of Italian libraries is the Anagrafe delle biblioteche italiane, managed by ICCU, the Istituto Centrale per il Catalogo Unico¹⁰. According to the Anagrafe, as of December 31, 2024, there are 13,639 libraries in Italy. Most libraries are described with a high level of detail, but for some, there is only identifying data and addresses. Moreover, some libraries do not update their data; only those libraries that have updated their data from 2020 to the present have been selected (11,710 libraries). Not all of them have the email address. Still, since the essential task of importing the Anagrafe of Italian Libraries into Wikidata was completed in 2024, it has been verified whether Wikidata contains more up-to-date data concerning the dataset, with a particular focus on the email addresses required to retrieve and send the questionnaire.

The final dataset to send the survey consists of 10,739 libraries with unique email addresses. A dedicated mailing list was populated with 10,739 email addresses to enable simultaneous reach of all target libraries and to facilitate easy sending of reminders.

The National Research Council (CNR) account sent the invitation email on February 5, 2025, and the questionnaire remained available until 3 March 2025. Reminders were repeated on 19 and 25 February. Reminders were also sent to the special libraries' mailing lists.

In **Spain**, a total of 7,640 email addresses were identified for Spanish libraries of all types, ranging from schools to national, public, and specialised libraries. This initial figure comprehensively covered virtually all Spanish libraries of all kinds.

The survey was distributed through two mass mailings, conducted on 5 February, with a reminder on the 19th of the same month. It was sent to approximately 7,640 email addresses, previously identified through the comprehensive lists available on Spain's Ministry of Culture website, covering virtually all libraries in the country. The delivery rate for these emails was 85.4%, leaving a final number of approximately 6,500 addresses.

FESABID distributed the questionnaire through a licensed software, Brevo, which allows for tracking of the percentage of opened emails, the click-through rate, the hard and soft bounces, and the email addresses of recipients. This enables better profiling of the mailing list for the reminder.

In **Poland**, the questionnaire was addressed to Polish libraries of all kinds, which were reached through professional Polish library associations and the Centrum Cyfrowe's professional network. As the survey was distributed directly by the library associations, the precise size of the population to which the survey was sent is unknown. Centrum Cyfrowe shared the information with a newsletter contact base consisting of 2,283 addresses (resulting in a total of 4,944 emails sent) and disseminated the survey on social media channels, including Facebook (9,800 followers) and LinkedIn (1,500 followers).

¹⁰ The Anagrafe of Italian libraries, available at <https://anagrafe.iccu.sbn.it/it/>

In **Italy**, the data collection process has generated a total of 440 completed questionnaires (corresponding to approximately 4.10% of the guests).

In **Spain**, the received responses are 179 (number corresponding to about 2,75% of the guests)

In **Poland**, the survey was filled in by representatives of 86 libraries. It is not possible to identify the total population of libraries reached (and so a response rate), given that distribution took place both via association mailing lists and social media.

III. The Results

A.1. Responses to Section I - LIBRARY'S PROFILE

Regarding the role of the respondent in the library, in Italy and Poland, the majority are library directors and librarians, with the remaining respondents holding other roles within the library. In Spain, the majority of respondents are either library technicians or library assistants.

The percentages of responses from different types of library, following IFLA's typology, are similar in the three countries; the majority are public libraries, followed by academic libraries. In Spain and Italy, the third category is the "Other" type, while all three countries received few replies from school libraries. National libraries replied in all three countries.

The types of collections held by the libraries in all three countries are very similar. The majority of respondents hold monographs, then serials, and then multimedia. The third category in Spain is digital resources, while in Italy, archival materials come first, followed by e-only resources. In all three countries, some respondents held public domain or out-of-copyright materials.

In the majority of cases the size of the library's physical collection is large. In Italy 41% report having a large collection, 36% a medium, and 21% a very large one. In Poland, the largest share stated that they had a very large physical collection¹¹ (43%), while 40,7% had a large, and 14 a medium collection. In Spain, over half reported that they had a large collection (50,30%), 27,4% a medium-sized one¹² and 18,4% a very large one. A very small percentage in Italy (2%), Spain (3,90%) and Poland (2,3%) declare a small¹³ physical collection.

Regarding the size of the library's digital collection, in all three countries, the largest share declare possessing a small digital collection (Italy 68%, Poland 41,9%, Spain 67%), while

¹¹ Very large (Over 50,000 records); Large (10,000–50,000 records).

¹² Medium (1,000–10,000 records).

¹³ Small (less than 1,000 records).

some declare a medium (Italy 16%, Poland 12,8%, Spain 15%), large (Italy 8%, Poland 9,3%, Spain 6%) or very large (Italy 8%, Poland 14%, Spain 18,40%) one.

Finally, in all three countries, the vast majority of respondents (between 70% and 75%) don't have a dedicated team to manage digital services or collections.

A.2. Responses to Section II - DIGITAL LENDING

The comparative analysis of the questionnaire responses from Italy, Spain, and Poland reveals notable differences in the development and perception of digital lending and (i)SDL services across the three countries.

Spain stands out as the most advanced in the implementation of digital lending, with over 50% of libraries offering some type of this service and a significant portion extending access to their entire collections.

Italy follows a more cautious approach, with only 36% of participating libraries offering e-lending, and the majority do so selectively, limiting digital access to specific resources.

Poland, by contrast, lags considerably behind, with more than 60% of libraries not engaged in digital lending, and many of those that demonstrate a lack of clarity regarding the scope or nature of their services.

This trend extends to the adoption of (i)SDL models: both Italy and Spain report minimal implementation (3.9% and 6.1%, respectively), while Poland indicates a near-total absence (74,4% stating no implementation, with almost all other responses being 'don't know').

In terms of the types of materials lent under (i)SDL, public domain works dominate in both Italy and Spain, due to the absence of copyright barriers around these. However, some efforts are made to include out-of-commerce or print-only in-copyright works. Poland, again, offers no substantial data.

User demand for (i)SDL is generally perceived as low or unclear across the board, with fewer than 10% of libraries in any country reporting high demand. Nevertheless, future outlooks differ: Spain shows relative optimism, with over 60% of its respondents foreseeing increased demand. However, Italy is more restrained, and Poland offers no forward-looking assessment.

Finally, when considering the strategic importance of (i)SDL, libraries in Italy and Spain largely regard it as necessary but not essential; however, a greater share of Spanish institutions (22%) identify it as crucial, compared to Italy (12%). In Poland, a clear institutional stance is lacking.

Overall, Spain appears to be leading the transition toward digital lending and (i)SDL, Italy is gradually building capacity while navigating structural and user-based challenges, and

Poland remains at an early, hesitant stage, reflecting both infrastructural and conceptual gaps.

A.3. Responses to Section III - LEGAL BARRIERS

The responses from Italy, Spain, and Poland to the section on legal barriers in the implementation of (i)SDL service reflect a shared and significant level of uncertainty regarding the national copyright frameworks governing this model.

In **Italy**, more than half of the libraries (54.8%) report being unaware of any specific legal authorisation for (i)SDL, while 37.5% believe such authorisation exists—typically under conditions that ensure copyright protection, such as DRM implementation, limited access duration, and alignment with exceptions for educational or research purposes. A smaller portion (5.2%) explicitly denies any legal provision for (i)SDL, referencing Italian copyright law (notably Article 69 of Law 633/1941) as only permitting lending of printed copies, thus excluding digital equivalents. This reveals a fragmented understanding: while some libraries rely on European directives or contractual agreements with publishers, others highlight the absence of a clear statutory foundation. When asked about the clarity of national legislation, nearly half (48.6%) of Italian libraries refrained from answering, and over a quarter (26.4%) declared it unclear, signalling both confusion and concern over legal ambiguity, which could act as a deterrent to innovation in digital lending.

In **Spain**, the legal uncertainty is even more pronounced: only 12% of libraries report any knowledge, however partial, of national copyright rules regarding (i)SDL, whereas over 88% do not. As for legislative clarity, 56% report being unaware of how clear the law is, 24% find it not clear at all, and only a minority perceives some level of clarity. These figures reflect a widespread knowledge gap that hampers legal confidence in offering digital lending services.

Poland shows a very similar pattern, with the vast majority of respondents unable to confirm whether national copyright law authorises (i)SDL, and very few able to articulate conditions under which SDL might be permissible, such as compliance with educational exceptions or the use of “one copy–one user” and time-limited loans. Notably, 35% of Polish libraries explicitly consider their legislation unclear, and 45% state they do not know, confirming the minimal institutional awareness of the legal framework.

Across all three countries, the survey reveals that the perceived or absolute lack of legal clarity constitutes a significant barrier to the adoption and expansion of (i)SDL. Italy appears slightly more advanced in terms of engaging with legal questions and attempting to interpret frameworks; however, overall, the data highlights the urgent need for more precise guidance, training, and possibly legislative reform to foster a coherent and confident approach to digital lending within the European library ecosystem.

A.4. Responses to Section IV - TECHNOLOGICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE BARRIERS

The analysis of technological and infrastructural barriers to (i)SDL implementation across Italy, Spain, and Poland reveals a broadly shared landscape of structural fragility, but with varying degrees of awareness, preparedness, and collaborative potential.

In **Italy**, the data shows that major technological obstacles are widely recognised: 167 libraries identify the lack of digitisation equipment as a significant barrier, while similarly high numbers point to the absence of robust archiving systems, DRM technologies or technical know-how. The predominance of these concerns suggests that while Italian libraries may conceptually support (i)SDL, they are often not equipped to implement it in practice. Notably, the relevant number of “don’t know” responses in each category (concerning lack of digitisation equipment, 7%; lack of an adequate archiving system, 10%; inadequate DRM, 10,2%) reflects both gaps in technical understanding and the need for more explicit guidance and capacity-building programs. DRM, in particular, stands out as a significant hurdle, with nearly half of the respondents flagging it as a critical challenge, indicating the complexities surrounding copyright compliance, user authentication, and secure access.

However, Italy also presents a relatively strong foundation in collaborative infrastructure, with 42.7% of libraries being part of consortia or partnerships that could facilitate resource sharing. These range from regional and municipal networks (such as SBV, SDIAF, and the Bergamo Library Network) to national hubs like SBN and NILDE, as well as thematic collaborations (e.g., Bibliosan). Although not all these systems are explicitly oriented towards (i)SDL, they offer promising starting points, especially where platforms like MLOL are already in place, for experimenting with or scaling up secure digital lending.

In **Spain**, the perception of technological barriers is similarly acute: 60–63% of libraries report major obstacles concerning access to all of digitisation equipment, archiving, and DRM systems, mirroring Italy’s findings. Notably, 43% also highlight a lack of staff expertise as a critical issue, and 37% admit they lack the knowledge to evaluate the technological context at all. This suggests a dual challenge: not only the absence of technical infrastructure, but also a widespread skills gap that may inhibit the design or management of digital lending services. Yet Spain reports greater integration in collaborative networks, with 59% of libraries belonging to wider systems, potentially placing them in a stronger position to develop shared solutions.

In **Poland**, the picture is even more challenging. Respondents overwhelmingly mark all three technological factors as significant barriers - digitisation equipment, archiving systems, and DRM - with additional concerns about limited staff competencies in the field. The lack of concrete examples or mentions of collaborative infrastructure further reinforces the impression that Polish libraries are, at present, structurally underprepared for implementing (i)SDL.

While recognising these challenges is an essential first step, the absence of coordinated efforts or networks to mitigate them highlights a critical need for strategic investment, training, and infrastructure development. Taken together, the responses from the three countries underscore an everyday European reality: the successful implementation of (i)SDL will depend not only on clarifying legal frameworks, but also on bridging the persistent technological divide through funding, staff development, and especially the strategic use of library consortia to pool resources, expertise, and infrastructure.

A.5. Responses to Section V - RISK OF OPPOSITION

The data on the perceived **risk of opposition** to implementing (i)SDL across libraries in **Italy, Spain, and Poland** reveals a pervasive atmosphere of uncertainty, both within institutions and in their relationship with external stakeholders, particularly publishers.

In **Italy**, over half of the respondents (50.9%) were unable to say whether internal resistance exists within their institutions, suggesting that decision-making processes around (i)SDL are either opaque or not broadly discussed among staff. Only 9% reported actual resistance, often associated with concerns around a lack of financial resources, staff shortages, outdated infrastructure, limited digital skills, or fear of copyright violations. The remaining 40% perceived no internal opposition, indicating some openness to innovation where conditions allow.

Spain displayed a similar pattern, with 53% unsure, 32% perceiving no resistance, and only 15% acknowledging it, a profile that again suggests internal hesitations are more a matter of unawareness than explicit opposition.

The picture changes only slightly when considering the external risks, particularly the fear of legal challenges from publishers or authors. In Italy, 52.5% of respondents admitted not knowing whether such concerns deter implementation, while 27.7% believed legal fears do play a role. A small minority (15.6%) denied this, suggesting that such fears are not universally internalised but may loom larger in environments where there is already uncertainty about legal frameworks. Spain shows a similar distribution, with a high level of uncertainty (61%) and only 16% recognising legal risks as a concrete deterrent.

When considering concerns about technological barriers as a driver of resistance, **Italian libraries** again show divided views: 46.6% don't know whether such obstacles deter (i)SDL, 33.4% affirm they do, and 17% deny it. Responses make it clear that technological concerns are closely linked to lack of funding, outdated equipment, and the absence of institutional support. The **Spanish** data echoes this, with 51% unsure, 26% confirming tech as a barrier, and 18% rejecting the idea.

Lastly, perceptions of the publishing industry's stance on (i)SDL are marked by scepticism and opacity across both countries. In **Italy**, a majority (53.4%) stated they don't know how

publishers would react, while 35.6% believe publishers are against the model, likely due to concerns over rights management and market control. Only a tiny fraction (0.9%) perceived publishers as supportive. **Spain** presents a slightly more optimistic view: while 40% of libraries are uncertain, 35% foresee opposition, 14% expect neutrality, and 11% anticipate a favourable response, suggesting that Spain's library ecosystem may have a marginally more dialogic relationship with the publishing sector. In **Poland**, although the detailed figures are unavailable, previous sections of the survey suggest similar or greater uncertainty, particularly due to limited awareness of legal and technological frameworks.

Across the board, these findings indicate that resistance to (i)SDL is less about overt opposition and more about hesitation, knowledge gaps, and structural uncertainty. The lack of strong affirmative or negative views highlights the need for more precise policy guidance, legal clarification, and enhanced internal communication within library systems, as well as open dialogue with the publishing industry to address concerns and explore cooperative models.

A.6. Responses To Section VI - HUMAN RESOURCES

The responses from Italy, Spain, and Poland to the section on human resources and expertise for implementing (i)SDL reveal a consistent pattern of significant structural limitations, marked by a lack of legal and technological support, minimal staff training, and a strong perceived need for professional development.

In **Italy**, only a small fraction of libraries (6–15%) report access to legal or technological expertise on (i)SDL-related issues, while the vast majority (around 70%) explicitly lack such support, and roughly 20% are unsure. Even where legal offices exist at institutional levels (e.g., universities), their focus is often too general to effectively address copyright issues specific to digital lending. Training for library staff is equally limited: 83% report no legal training, and 79% no technological training, with just over 10% stating they have received limited instruction. The obstacles behind this lack of preparation are well documented by respondents and include chronic underfunding, staff shortages, reliance on volunteers or unqualified personnel, and institutional indifference toward library development.

In many cases, training depends on individual initiative, with some librarians pursuing education at their own expense or outside working hours. Despite these barriers, there is overwhelming recognition of the need for improvement: 77% believe legal training is necessary, and the same percentage affirms the need for technological training. These figures are slightly higher in **Spain**, where 87% of respondents express the need for legal and technological training, reinforcing the idea that while knowledge is currently lacking, awareness of the gap is widespread and strongly felt. Spain also mirrors **Italy** in terms of existing conditions: only 15% report access to legal advice, 9% to technological expertise, and more than 70% of respondents confirm that no training has been delivered on either front.

The case of **Poland** reinforces and amplifies these concerns. Legal and technological infrastructure for (i)SDL is virtually absent: only 23% of libraries have access to legal experts, and 64% lack any form of technological support. Training is equally scarce, yet 73% of Polish respondents agree that legal training is necessary, and 70% request technological instruction, underscoring that the desire to engage with (i)SDL is present but unsupported by institutions.

What emerges across all three countries is a clear and pressing human resource gap that threatens to impede the broader adoption of secure digital lending. Libraries often lack both the internal expertise and the institutional support necessary to navigate the legal and technical complexities of (i)SDL, and this is compounded by long-standing issues like underfunding, precarious staffing, and a failure to make libraries a policy priority.

However, the responses also reveal a strong willingness among professionals to engage with these challenges, provided that training, guidance, and strategic support become available. In short, the human capacity to implement (i)SDL exists in potential, but activating it requires systematic investment and recognition of libraries as vital institutions in the digital transition.

A.7. Responses To Section VII - FINANCIAL BARRIERS

The responses from libraries in Italy, Spain, and Poland to the section on financial barriers to implementing (i)SDL reveal a consistent picture of economic constraints that, if unaddressed, risk limiting the potential of (independent) Secure Digital Lending. However, these results should not be interpreted as indicating that legal change would have no effect. On the contrary, **clarifying the legal framework is a crucial prerequisite to unlock investment and strategic prioritisation** by both institutions and policymakers.

In **Italy**, 65.6% of respondents state that their library does not currently have adequate financial resources to implement (i)SDL, while only 6.3% confirm having sufficient funding. Nearly 28% are unsure, reflecting not only structural funding challenges but also a lack of transparency or awareness around budget allocations. When asked about the affordability of digitisation tools and DRM systems, 57.5% of Italian libraries deem them unaffordable, 15.4% say they are affordable, and 27% do not know. This indicates that cost is perceived as a barrier, but also suggests limited involvement of library staff in procurement processes and infrastructure decisions.

In **Spain**, 72% of respondents confirm that their institutions lack the necessary budget to implement (i)SDL, 22% are uncertain, and only 6% report having the required funding. Additionally, Spanish libraries show lower access to digitisation tools and DRM systems: 46% say they cannot access such tools, 45% are unsure, and only 8% affirm they have

them. This combination of budget scarcity and limited awareness highlights an area where both financial investment and institutional collaboration can be strengthened.

Similarly, in **Poland**, 64% of libraries report insufficient funding to support (i)SDL implementation, with digitisation alone already described as a “great challenge.”

However, while financial barriers are real, they do not negate the need for legal reform. **On the contrary, clear legal authorisation for (i)SDL can provide the certainty required to justify investment and resource allocation**, enabling libraries to plan strategically, seek funding, and prioritise digital transformation in their services. Moreover, the high percentages of “don’t know” responses across all questions suggest that improving legal clarity, training, and institutional governance could empower libraries to engage more proactively in budgeting and technological planning processes.

Ultimately, financial investment and legal reform must go hand in hand. Without coordinated public support, targeted funding programs, and clearer legislation, even the most motivated libraries will struggle to move beyond pilot projects. But with these elements in place, the widespread interest in (i)SDL shown by libraries across all three countries can translate into tangible, sustainable digital lending services that fulfil their mission in the digital age.

A.8. Responses To Section VIII - OTHERS

The final section of the survey, dedicated to “other” considerations, offers a nuanced and future-oriented perspective on the broader needs, expectations, and uncertainties surrounding (i)SDL across libraries in Italy, with comparative insight from Spain and Poland.

In **Italy**, a significant majority (69.3%) of respondents expressed a clear desire for more information and training opportunities on (i)SDL, suggesting strong professional interest but also a gap in accessible resources and knowledge. This finding is echoed in **Spain**, where 83% report the same need, and in **Poland**, where, despite limited current understanding, there is evident demand for capacity-building and awareness-raising.

Italian respondents were also invited to reflect on **what national policymakers should do** to support (i)SDL adoption. Their answers emphasise four main areas: **training** (26.1%), **funding** (17.4%), **legal reform** (13%), and **technical infrastructure** (13%). These priorities confirm that the successful implementation of (i)SDL is perceived as dependent on coordinated policy action that empowers libraries with skills, resources, and legal clarity, needs that are similarly articulated in **Spain** and **Poland**.

Regarding the future relevance of (i)SDL, most **Italian** respondents (62.2%) believe it will become increasingly important for libraries, citing reasons such as digital transformation, user expectations for remote access, inclusivity, and preservation of collections. This belief is slightly more cautious in **Spain**, where 48% foresee growing relevance, while in **Poland**, 53% anticipate an inevitable shift toward digital lending, especially in academic and research

contexts.

However, across countries, a significant proportion—34.7% in **Italy**, 35% in **Spain**, and 40% in **Poland**, responded “don’t know,” revealing persistent uncertainty due to legal ambiguity, variable user needs, and infrastructural disparities.

When asked whether (i)SDL systems could integrate with existing platforms and catalogues, 58.1% of **Italian** libraries answered affirmatively, reflecting cautious optimism about technical feasibility, although nearly 40% remain unsure. A similar trend is seen in **Spain**, where 67% believe integration is possible. On the issue of data protection, **Italian** libraries were more hesitant: 53.1% stated they didn’t know whether (i)SDL could guarantee the security of personal and digital content data, while 40.6% believed it could. **Spain** showed slightly greater confidence in this area, with 59% affirming compatibility between SDL and data protection standards. These figures indicate a need for more transparent communication around the privacy safeguards and technical design of (i)SDL systems.

The final question explored the consequences of not implementing (i)SDL, revealing a shared recognition of the risks of inaction. In **Italy**, the most frequently cited concern (33.3%) was that users who cannot physically visit the library and for whom no commercial e-book version exists are effectively denied access. Other problems included reduced competitiveness (27.5%), decreased user engagement (10.1%), and weakened library-user relationships (6.7%). Comparable concerns were raised in **Spain and Poland**, where respondents highlighted the risk of losing cultural relevance, becoming non-competitive in the digital ecosystem, and failing to fulfil libraries’ public-interest missions.

Nevertheless, a minority of respondents **across all countries** questioned whether (i)SDL is necessary, particularly where digital services are already provided through national platforms or where print media remains central to the community.

In summary, Italian libraries, like their Spanish and Polish counterparts, view (i)SDL as an opportunity aligned with the evolution of library services, but one that remains constrained by gaps in training, funding, legal certainty, and infrastructural support. There is strong interest and cautious optimism about its relevance and feasibility, alongside persistent questions about implementation, integration, and sustainability. If policymakers and stakeholders respond with appropriate structural and educational support, (i)SDL could become a cornerstone of a more inclusive, accessible, and future-ready library system.

IV. Conclusions

The comparative survey conducted across libraries in Italy, Spain, and Poland reveals a shared aspiration toward implementing (independent) Secure Digital Lending - (i)SDL - services but underscores significant systemic barriers that hinder progress. While Spain demonstrates relatively greater advancement in digital lending adoption, followed by Italy, Poland remains in an early, exploratory phase.

Across all three countries, the principal barriers to (i)SDL adoption are consistently legal uncertainty, technological fragility, inadequate funding, and insufficient human resource capacity. Legal frameworks are perceived as ambiguous or unknown by a majority of respondents, causing institutional hesitation and a lack of confidence in offering (i)SDL services. Technologically, most libraries lack digitisation infrastructure, DRM systems, and archival solutions, and are not supported by trained staff.

Despite these challenges, the survey also highlights a strong desire for professional development, greater legal clarity, and strategic investment. A significant proportion of libraries recognise the potential of (i)SDL to support digital transformation, enhance user access, and preserve cultural resources. Respondents in all three countries agree that failure to implement (i)SDL may result in digital exclusion, reduced attractiveness, and weakened public service relevance. It is to be noted, in particular, that clear legal authorisation for (i)SDL has the potential to provide the certainty required to justify investment and resource allocation.

In conclusion, the successful implementation of (i)SDL across European libraries depends on coordinated efforts at both national and international levels. This includes clear legal guidelines, dedicated funding schemes, capacity-building programs, and collaborative infrastructures. Only through structural investment and policy commitment can libraries fully embrace the opportunities of digital lending and fulfill their evolving mission in the digital age.

Future research directions

Based on the findings of this survey, several avenues for future research and development emerge:

1. **Longitudinal tracking of (i)SDL implementation** – Repeating the survey over time (e.g., every 2 years) would allow researchers to monitor trends, identify shifts in adoption, and evaluate the impact of policy interventions.
2. **Expansion of the survey to other EU Countries** – Including countries such as France, Germany, Greece, and the Netherlands would provide a more comprehensive European picture and enrich the comparative dataset.
3. **Human capital and skills gap assessment** – Targeted studies on the legal and digital competencies of library staff could inform the design of effective training programs and institutional capacity-building strategies.
4. **Technical integration and interoperability research** – Exploring how (i)SDL systems can be effectively integrated with existing catalogues, repositories, and platforms could inform the creation of shared standards.

5. **Social impact studies** – Focused research on how (i)SDL can promote equity in access to knowledge, especially for rural, disabled, or socio-economically disadvantaged users, would support inclusive policy development.

Appendix A- Questionnaire

Questionnaire on the barriers to the adoption of (independent) Secure Digital Lending (iSDL): Legal, technical, and operational challenges.

This questionnaire results from an initiative of [Knowledge Rights 21](#) (KR21) aimed at gathering information from libraries in Italy, Poland, and Spain concerning (independent) **Secure Digital Lending (iSDL) — e-lending based on paper books digitised by libraries where some protection measures are adopted to prevent non-legitimate uses (for instance, measures to limitate the lending time, to prevent downloading, etc. often named DRM Digital Rights Management Systems)**¹⁴. It investigates the legal, technical, and other barriers that influence the potential for further adoption of (i)SDL.

The partners of this research project are:

Italy: [STUDIO LEGALE DDA](#); [CLAKP](#) (Copyright Law and Access to Knowledge Policies Group) conceived and developed by IGSG (Istituto di Informatica Giuridica e Sistemi Giudiziari)/CNR (Consiglio Nazionale delle Ricerche)

Poland: [CENTRUM CYFROWE](#)

Spain: [FESABID](#)

The project explores these issues to lay the groundwork for identifying the key challenges and potential benefits behind (i)SDL implementation. The project outcomes could provide a foundation for future strategies to overcome these obstacles and support the mission of libraries in the digital realm.

The questionnaire is divided into eight sections and contains **36 questions**.

Given the topic's relevance, please take about **20 minutes** to respond to the questionnaire we have prepared.

¹⁴ E-lending in the (i)SDL model was developed as part of the report *eBooks and Secure Digital Lending in European Libraries* (scheduled for publication in January/February 2025). In detail, e-lending based on the (i)SDL model is characterised by the following features: 1) Loans are made by strictly defined entities - establishments accessible to the public (e.g., libraries) that derive no direct or indirect economic or commercial advantage from their lending activity (requirement for a special case); 2) Lending covers the lending of a digital copy of a book; 3) Loans are made under the one copy - one user model; 4) Lending is carried out in a mimetic (i.e., allowing patrons to download electronic copies of books) or a quasi-mimetic fashion (i.e., allowing the use of electronic copies of books in streaming); 5) Lending is only for a limited period; 6) After the lending period has expired, the user cannot use the e-book; 7) A digital copy of a book must be obtained from a lawful source, but the library can make an electronic copy of a legally obtained copy of a paper book; e-lending under the (i)SDL model gives rise to the right to remuneration (PLR) in line with the Rental and Lending Directive; 8) there is no transfer of data, including personal data of library patrons, to publishers or other third parties.

The deadline for completing the questionnaire is **February 26th, 2025.**

We greatly appreciate your participation in this survey, as your responses will directly contribute to shaping the future of (i)SDL in libraries across Europe.

I. LIBRARY'S PROFILE

1. For which library are you responding to this questionnaire? (Add the library's name)

Indicate the ISIL code (in the ICCU registry) of your library¹⁵

2. What is your role in the library?

3. What type of library are you answering for? Following [IFLA's typology](#):

- National
- Academic
- Public
- School
- Other

4. What types of collections does your library primarily hold?

(Select all that apply)

- Serials (e.g., journals, magazines, periodicals)
- Monographs (e.g., books, reports)
- Archival materials (e.g., manuscripts, historical documents)
- Multimedia (e.g., DVDs, audio recordings, images)
- Digital-only resources (e.g., e-books, databases, online journals)
- Public domain or out-of-copyright materials
- Other (please specify) _____

5. What is the size of your library's physical collection?

¹⁵ This question was only in the Italian questionnaire

- Small (less than 1,000 records)
- Medium (1,000–10,000 records)
- Large (10,000–50,000 records)
- Very large (Over 50,000 records)

6. What is the size of your library's digital collection?

- Small (less than 1,000 records)
- Medium (1,000–10,000 records)
- Large (10,000–50,000 records)
- Very large (Over 50,000 records)

7. Does your library have a dedicated team to manage digital services or collections?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

II. DIGITAL LENDING

8. Does your library provide an e-lending service?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

9. If you answer “yes” to the question above, please specify your library's current digital lending model.

- Digital lending provided for specific resources
- Digital lending fully provided
- I don't know

10. Does your library digitise physical works and lend digital copies under (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

11. If you answer “yes” to the question above, which of the following types of material do you lend under (i)SDL?

(Select all that apply)

- Public domain works

- In-copyright works which are out of commerce
- In-copyright works which are on sale but only in paper format
- In-copyright works which are on sale, also in electronic format
- Other (please specify) _____
- I don't know

12. Is there/would there be a demand for (i)SDL services from your library's users?

- Yes, there is high demand
- Yes, but the demand is moderate
- Very little demand
- No demand
- I don't know

Please specify your answer

13. Do you foresee that this demand, in the coming years, will:

- Increase strongly
- Increase marginally
- Stay stable
- Decline
- I don't know

14. In your opinion, how important is it for your library to offer a (i)SDL service?

- Essential
- Important but not essential
- Not important
- I don't know

Please explain why:

III. LEGAL BARRIERS

15. Does your national copyright law or other legislation authorise (i)SDL, and under what conditions?

16. How clear is your country's national copyright law or other legislation regarding (i)SDL?

- Very clear
- Somewhat clear

- Not clear at all
- I don't know

IV. TECHNOLOGICAL AND INFRASTRUCTURE BARRIERS

17. What technological barriers has your library encountered – or might encounter – in implementing (i)SDL?

(Please rate each barrier on a scale from 0 to 5, where 0=I don't know, 1 = Not a barrier and 5 = Major barrier)

Barrier	0=I don't know	1 (Not a barrier)	2	3	4	5 (Major barrier)
Lack of adequate digitisation equipment	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Lack of an adequate archiving system	<input type="checkbox"/>					
Inadequate digital rights management (DRM) system or lack of technical protection measures know-how	<input type="checkbox"/>					

If you think there are other technological barriers, please indicate them below:

18. Is your library part of a consortium or collaboration that could share technological resources or infrastructures to enable (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

If you answered Yes, please specify which consortium or collaboration

V. RISK OF OPPOSITION

19. Do you face resistance from within your institution (e.g., staff or administration) to implementing (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

If you answered "Yes" to the previous question, please specify

20. In your opinion, are libraries in your country reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential legal actions from publishers or authors?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Other (please specify) _____

21. In your opinion, are libraries in your country reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential technological barriers?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know
- Other (please specify) _____

22. How would the publishing industry in your country respond to the idea of (i)SDL?

- Strongly supportive
- Neutral
- Opposed
- I don't know

VI. HUMAN RESOURCES

23. Does your library have access to legal expertise to address copyright and (i)SDL-related issues?

- Yes, we have dedicated legal staff or advisor
- No, we lack the necessary legal support
- Other (please specify) _____
- I don't know

24. Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's legal aspects?

- Yes, extensive training
- Yes, but limited training
- No training has been provided
- In progress
- I don't know

If you answer "No" or "In progress" to the question above, please explain any challenges related to human resources:

25. Do you think such legal training or guidance is necessary?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

26. Does your library have access to technological expertise to address (i)SDL-related issues?

- Yes, we have dedicated staff or advisor
- No, we lack the necessary technological support
- Other (please specify) _____
- I don't know

27. Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's technological aspects (e.g., digital rights management, archiving systems, etc.)?

- Yes, extensive training
- Yes, but limited training
- No training has been provided
- In progress
- I don't know

If you answer “No” or “In progress” to the question above, please explain any challenges related to human resources:

28. Do you think such technological training or guidance is necessary?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

VII. FINANCIAL BARRIERS

29. Does your library have adequate financial resources to implement (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

30. Are digitisation tools and DRM systems affordable for the library?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

VIII. OTHER

31. Would you or your staff benefit from more information/formative events on (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

32. In your opinion, what steps should national policymakers take to facilitate (i)SDL adoption in libraries?

33. Do you think (i)SDL will become more relevant for libraries in the future?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

Please specify why

34. Could the library's (i)SDL system integrate with existing catalogues and platforms?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

35. Can the library secure users' personal and digital content data by providing (i)SDL?

- Yes
- No
- I don't know

36. What are the negative consequences of not providing (i)SDL?

(Select all that apply)

- The library loses its relationship with users
- The library cannot allow a user to read a book if he/she cannot go to the library personally and the publisher has not provided an e-book version of the book.
- Users are less likely to engage with the library's services
- The library may face increased pressure to offer digital access options
- The library's services become less competitive than other libraries or digital platforms.
- There are none
- Other (please specify) _____
- I don't know

Appendix B - Excerpt of the most significant free-text comments

ITALY

1. Comment to question n. 12 “Is there/would there be a demand for (i)SDL services from your library’s users?”:
“Since it is not a service that is accessible, publicised, or in some cases even known, it is therefore not requested as much as it would deserve.”
2. Comment to question n. 14 “In your opinion, how important is it for your library to offer a (i)SDL service?”:
“Because technology advances, and it is unrealistic to expect libraries to continue offering the same services as 20 or 30 years ago. They need to adapt to the new needs of users and the opportunities offered by digital technologies.”
3. Comment to question n. 14 “In your opinion, how important is it for your library to offer a (i)SDL service?”:
In an era where digital access to resources is increasingly in demand, the possibility of consulting content online greatly enhances accessibility for all users, including those who are unable to visit the library in person. Furthermore, offering a digital service allows libraries to expand the resources available and to preserve and enhance their collections through innovative solutions. All of this meets current needs and helps make the library a cultural and educational reference point accessible to a wider audience.
4. Comment to question n. 27 “Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL’s technological”:
“Lack of staff dedicated to digitisation”.
5. Comment to question n. 27 “Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL’s technological”:
“Lack of staff training”.

SPAIN

1. Regarding question 12 of the questionnaire, (*Is there/would there be a demand for (i)SDL services from your library’s users?*) one respondent, a public library director, stated:
“When that possibility is offered, I estimate there will be considerable demand.”
2. Regarding question 17 of the questionnaire (*What technological barriers has your library encountered – or might encounter – in implementing (i)SDL?*), a respondent, director of

a university library, opines:

“Each publisher chooses a different way to lend their electronic books, and it is not possible to implement them all efficiently.”

3. Regarding question 20 of the questionnaire (*In your opinion, are libraries in your country reluctant to implement (i)SDL because of concerns about potential legal actions from publishers or authors?*), a respondent, service manager at the documentation center of an art museum, responds:
“If it is carried out within the law, there is no reason to fear a negative reaction from publishers, authors, or copyright management societies.”
4. In the comments related to question 24 of the questionnaire (*Has your library staff received training or guidance on (i)SDL's legal aspects?*), a respondent, an assistant technician in a public library, states that they have not received any type of training, and requests:
“Courses and training should be planned (both for people who have just started and for those who have been working for years).”
5. Regarding question 32 of the questionnaire (*In your opinion, what steps should national policymakers take to facilitate (i)SDL adoption in libraries?*), a respondent, a librarian in a public library, states the following:
“All necessary measures: from the payment of licenses to legal advice, courses and training, etc.”

POLAND

What the policymakers should do:

1. *First and foremost, it's essential to establish legal frameworks that ensure libraries do not feel anxious about implementation (i.e., fear of legal liability). In my opinion, libraries should be privileged institutions and subject to a different set of copyright laws.*
2. *Clear legal regulations; no penalties for the unintentional sharing of a book for which permission was not obtained.*
 1. *A clear legal interpretation of what is allowed and what is not.*
 2. *An open technical specification for the information/IT system enabling (i)SDL — outlining the required standards so that it can be developed using various tools, including existing systems.*
 3. *A nationwide campaign targeting library directors and legal advisors — “Yes, you can do this!”*

3. *To facilitate the implementation of (i)SDL in libraries, national policymakers should take a range of actions to ensure legal compliance, improve access to resources, provide financial support to libraries, and at the same time protect the rights of creators. Policymakers should also strive to maintain a balance between providing broad access to educational resources and ensuring appropriate protection of creators' rights and fair compensation.*

On technological support:

4. *It's hard to say — when we create a system, we build it functionally based on our own knowledge and ideas (or ones we've observed elsewhere). However, the actual implementation in the system is done by the developer. Ideally, we would have access to an IT-IP lawyer who could assess whether our ideas are legally sound or if something needs to be adjusted. At the moment, this responsibility falls on us — more specifically, voluntarily on me and officially on our in-house lawyer.*
5. *We did not plan for such services outside of our collaboration with the Library Deposit.*